

HYBRID DNA BASED STEGNOGRAPHY

Abdul Haseeb A Neethu Premraj E.P Nehla Sruthi P.K
Mentor- Hrudya K.P

Department Of Computer Science And Engineering, IES College Of Engineering,
Calicut University, Thrissur, Kerala, India

Abstract:

Objective-The information capacity is growing significantly as well as its level of importance and its transformation rate. In this paper, a blind data hiding hybrid technique is introduced using the concepts of cryptography and steganography in order to achieve double layer secured system.

Phases-The proposed method consists of two phases: phase one is converting the message to DNA format using the proposed n-bits binary coding rule leading to high algorithm's cracking probability compared with those of other algorithms. Followed by applying the Playfair cipher based on DNA and amino acids to encrypt the secret message which generates ambiguity. Phase two is hiding the cipher secret message parts with the ambiguity results from from the first phase. The data is hidden using the least significant base (LSBase) only of each codon of a selected DNA reference sequence using 3:1 hiding strategy. The proposed technique achieves hiding the data in DNA with preserving its biological functions as possible without requiring any extra data to be sent to the receiver.

Keywords: DNA Encryption, Playfair Cipher, Steganography, DNA Decryption.

I. INTRODUCTION

As some of the modern cryptography algorithms (such as DES, and more recently, MD5) are broken, the new directions of information security are being sought to protect the data. The concept of using DNA computing in the fields of cryptography and steganography is a possible technology that may bring forward a new hope for powerful, or even unbreakable, algorithms. The main purpose behind our work is to discover new fields of encoding the data in addition to

the conventional used encryption algorithm in order to increase the concept of confusion and therefore increase security. In our work, we applied the conversion of character form or binary form of data to the DNA form and then to amino acid form. Then the resulting form goes through the encryption algorithm which we chose for example; the classical Playfair cipher.

II. RELATED WORK

2.1 DNA-GENETIC ENCRYPTION TECHNIQUE

This paper proposes DNA-Genetic Encryption Technique (D-GET) that is an iterative algorithm in order to enhance information security. Any type of data (i.e. message, image, video or signal) can be encrypted. The main steps of proposed technique are pre-processing, symmetric key encryption, reshaping and crossover and mutation. The main stages of D-GET are repeated three times or more. Transmit the encrypted data in text/image format file. In other side, the receiver uses the D-GET to decrypt the received data and reshape it to original format. This Technique also transforms the text into an image and vice versa to improve security and multiple key sequences to increase the degree of diffusion and confusion, which makes resulting cipher data difficult to decipher and makes to realize a perfect secrecy system. Experimental results demonstrate that proposed technique has multilayer protection stages against different attacks and higher level of security based on the multi-stages and genetic operations. Decrypted data are acceptable because of there is absolutely difference between it and secret data. The negligible relationship in both the secret data and its encrypted-data reduces the possibilities of cryptanalysis and breaking the cipher.

2.2 AN IMPROVED DNA BASED DUAL COVER STEGANOGRAPHY

The proposed work concentrates on hiding secret data in multiple layers of cover media. The DNA is attributed by the pixel properties of the image. Thus this procedure makes it more secured than the methods using reference DNAs from public databases. This algorithm improves the existing dual cover steganography by reducing the noise bits in the secondary cover. Moreover the algorithm is modified to accommodate secret image message (both 24-bit and 8-bit) in the cover. The entire process consists of Prepare secret data and verify length constraints, Embedding process of secret data, Extraction process of secret data. Our secret message length varies from 2500 bases to 160000 bases. The algorithm hides 2 bits (1 base) per pixel. Multiple

keys are required for the entire process starting from DNA construction to data embedding and their transfer between sender and receiver requires a secure key exchange protocol.

2.3 A NOVEL APPROACH TOWARDS DEVELOPMENT OF HYBRID IMAGE STEGANOGRAPHY USING DNA SEQUENCES

This paper describes an algorithm for data hiding inside a DNA sequence. Encryption is a process by which we encode the data inside the image. Decryption is the reverse process of encryption that is extraction of bits from image file. ENCRYPTION: In first phase a secret data is encrypted in a DNA sequence and then second phase the encrypted data is encode in a cover image and the authentication values are needed. The data is encoded with the stego-key inside DNA sequences. Then this encrypted data again will be encrypted with the same stego-key. Then the final data will be encoded inside the image file along with the authentication key and the encrypted image will be called stego-image. DECRYPTION: The data is extracted from stego-image using proper authentication value and then decrypt the extracted bit using stego-key by which we get the original DNA sequence and then from the sequence get the original data. In the decryption process we have a stego-image and valid authentication key and a stego-key. Valid Authentication key will give access to actual decryption module otherwise return with failure. In decryption module DNA-encrypted bits are extracted from the image and using valid stego-key encrypted bits are decoded into actual raw bits. If the stego-key is wrong then decrypted module generate a garbage bit stream. The stego-image must be formed with raw pixel values, because almost every image compression algorithms are loss, so if you apply such algorithms then the pixel values will be altered and create a corrupted stego-image. Image type like 'jpg', 'jpeg' must be avoided and prefer image type like 'bmp'. It gives 3-level of security and an authenticity mechanism.

Three levels are • Data Hiding in DNA Sequence or Data Retrieval from DNA Sequence.
• Roundup Summation or Subtraction. • Encoding the Byte Streams in Pixel or Decode the Byte Streams From pixels. Innovative

2.4 APPROACH TO IMPROVE HYBRID CRYPTOGRAPHY BY USING DNA STEGANOGRAPHY.

This is a technique using a combination of cryptographic and steganography techniques. The method answers to requirements of a secure communication while defeating most of the popular attacks known up until today. In this paper, it does not want to focus on approach to exchange DNA steganography, but use hybrid cryptosystem based on DNA steganography. Sender and receiver use following protocol to exchange the session key. For the first communication, 1. Alice communicates with Bob to share a secret key (DNA steganography key). 2. Bob receives the steganography key and uses it to embed the symmetric key in a DNA stream 3. Alice receives the DNA stream, extracts the symmetric key and the symmetric connection is established. For all next communications, 1. Alice embeds a new symmetric key in a DNA stream, sends it to Bob. 2. Using the same DNA Steganography key, Bob extracts the symmetric key and generates a symmetric connection. The main advantage of this cryptography protocol was using innovative DNA steganography techniques to conceal secret session key which is transferred among sender and receiver throughout unsecured channel. In this protocol attackers are not aware of exchanging session key which is hidden by DNA data hiding method. The strength point of the DNA steganography algorithm is using DNA reference sequences which are selected from EBI database. It have approximately 163 million DNA sequences from EBI database. It is impossible for attackers to find whether or not there are secret message hidden in DNA sequences. Even if attackers know a secret message is embedded in DNA sequences, it is impossible to guess the correct sequence among 163 million DNA sequences.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed scheme consists of two phases: the first one is converting the secret message to DNA by mapping the binary bits to DNA nucleotides using a proposed n-bits binary coding rule. N-bits binary coding rule works on mapping n-bits from the message to m-bases of DNA and in this paper 4-bits binary coding rule is considered. Then, the DNA and amino acids based Playfair cipher encrypts the encrypted message. Then, the ciphered message is hidden in a selected DNA sequence from NCBI database using the LSBase method. So, the first contribution is providing double layer security system by developing a hybrid technique to hide the encrypted secret data in DNA results in high security as will further discussed in the security analysis section. The second contribution is using n-bits binary coding rule to convert the binary format of a text to DNA that results in increasing the algorithm's cracking probability in obvious way.

Finally, the third contribution is the innovation idea 3:1 ratio used in the data hiding technique. This strategy hides the secret data in DNA using LSBase method which results in avoiding extra data to be sent to the receiver.

Figure 3.1 System Architecture

3.1 DNA ENCRYPTION

In DNA Encryption ASCII of the corresponding plain text message is converted to binary(Mbin).Mbin is then converted to DNA using proposed 4-bits binary coding rule. Then, the DNA format is converted to amino acids and AMBIGbin is generated from decimal digits by mapping each two bits to apply the Playfair cipher on it using the secret key .

3.2 PLAYFAIR ENCRYPTION

The proposed technique uses DNA and amino acids Playfair cipher to encrypt the secret message some modifications to the conventional Playfair cipher by utilizing some biological concepts as DNA and amino acids to strengthen the ordinary Playfair cipher. In the proposed algorithm, DNA and amino acids based Playfair cipher is applied.

3.3 PLAYFAIR DECRYPTION

The receiver applies the Playfair cipher to decrypt the message using the secret key. Both sender and receiver will share the secret key from the beginning. But sharing a secret key may possess a problem since it needs to be interchanged before applying the encryption process. To avoid this problem, the proposed method can be modified to hide the secret key within the faked sequence. At the receiver side, when the faked DNA sequence S^* is sent to the receiver without any additional data which enhances the algorithm's security,

3.4 STEGANOGRAPHY

Steganography is the science and art of information hiding. Every method that includes Steganography uses an algorithm that embeds the data into a carrier and employs a detector function that retrieves back the embedded information. Steganography algorithms can be categorized into two categories of spatial/time domain and transform domain techniques. LSB method is spatial/time domain type of steganography where the information is embedded in the spatial domain of the image or time domain of audio carrier. This method plays with the binary representation of the hidden data. Least significant base is the data hiding methodology proposed. In a DNA sequence each three adjacent nucleotides constitute a unit called codon. LSB method depends on hiding the secret message bits in the least significant bit of each codon of the reference sequence.

3.5 DNA DECRYPTION

Decryption is the inverse of the encryption phase, where M_{bin} is converted to DNA using proposed 4-bits binary coding rule. Then, the ciphered DNA format is converted to amino acids to apply the Playfair cipher on it using the secret key. Decrypted amino acids form is generated from Playfair cipher then $AMBIG_{bin}$ is converted to decimal digits by mapping each two bits to number. Use each ambiguity number with each amino acid character to retrieve the corresponding codon to this char associated with this ambiguity number. Finally, a sequence of DNA is retrieved, by converting it into binary using 4-bits binary coding rule then to ASCII to get the corresponding plain text which is the original form of the secret data.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a data hiding method is proposed by combining the means of cryptography and steganography as well. This achieves double layer security of the system. A new binary coding rule is proposed that assigns $2n$ bits to each combination of n nucleotides instead of assigning two bits to only one nucleotide which increase the number of rules from $4!$ to $(2n*2n)!$ binary coding rules leads to strengthen the algorithm's security. Due to using LSB method in hiding the cipher bits of the message and the ambiguity, the proposed algorithm is still blind as the embedded data can be extracted without the need to the original DNA reference sequence. The proposed method also doesn't expand the real DNA reference sequence. It preserves the original DNA sequence length as it depends on substitution only so the algorithm's payload is zero which avoids attracting the attention to the faked sequence. As a future work, the proposed method can be modified to increase the hiding capacity of the DNA sequence with increasing the algorithm's security too.

V. REFERENCES

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